

On the Concept of Reduplication in Linguistics

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ABSTRACT: This article is devoted to the study of the notion of reduplication in linguistics; the concepts of full, partial are given. marvel reduplication and features of their construction. Reduplication in terms of expression is not limited to repeating the same units or repeating only one basis and syllable. Repetitions are also considered as repetitions associated with the complete or partial repetition of a reductive sound, as well as “repetition of synonymous lexical units, that is, the creation of repeats of a value. Their functional, structural, semantic capabilities are described only in general terms”.

KEYWORDS: Doubling, Morpheme, Phoneme, Repetition, Reduplication, Service Words, Significant Words, Significant Part Of Word, Word Formation

INTRODUCTION

“Reduplication” means “repetition”, “doubling” [1, p. 26], this method is a method of re-word formation [2, p. 101].

A recurring word is a word that is formed by reusing the same word [2, p. 102]. According to A. Khodjiev, the repeated word expresses such meanings as the majority (multiplicity) and duration.

If, bypassing the word-forming function of repetition, one considers only its word-forming function, then repetition acts as a formal means expressing different meanings. For example, the reduction expresses a) the enhanced (reduced) character of adjectives; b) duration, intensity, repetition of verbs; c) collective or distributive values within substantive values; r) expressive-methodological function.

All these values can also be expressed by other means of language.

This approach corresponds to S.Kartsevsky’s “asymmetric dualism of a linguistic unit”. [3, p. 209].

What is the difference between “repetition” and “reduplication”?

Not all words called “repetitive” are considered reductive. For example: when talking about “repetitive” verb is understood verb expressing repetition of action: “kick”, “pull” [4, p. 110]. “Reductive verb” on the other hand indicates partial or full dual form of verb: “plenty of” (play). Repetition also expresses the use of the same word in two or more cases as a syntactic unit: “Don’t be afraid, Don’t be afraid, - repeated Arslon aka” [2, p. 101].

Reduplication, however, does not have this function. When “reduplicating” is understood the way of repeated word formation. Based on the subject of the study, our study used the term “reduplication”. Since the word “repetition”, as noted above, is broader than reduplication.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

In the book by D.E.Rosenthal and M.A.Telenkova “Dictionary-directory of linguistic terms” reduplication is interpreted as “repetition” [5, p. 286]. “Repetition” means one of the ways in which words, phraseological units, descriptive forms are created by reusing a certain basis of a word or a whole word [5, p. 288].

There are several types of repetitions. This is grammatical repetition, imitative repetition, lexical repetition and stylistic repetition.

“Grammatical repetition” means ways of expressing grammatical meanings, constructing word forms [5, p. 457]. Such methods include synthetic, analytical and hybrid (mixed) methods.

Another type of repetition is imitation repetition. This means words that arise by imitation of the voice of living and inanimate objects, movement and the image (silhouette) of objects (“gig-gig” (*vjik-vjik*), “boom-boom”, etc.).

In lexical repetition, word repetition is used: 1) to express the multiplicity of phenomena and objects, 2) to enhance the action, quality, property of an object, 3) to indicate the duration of action.

Methodical repetition means repetition of words in a sentence in order to increase expressiveness [5, p. 286].

The article studies grammatical, imitative and lexical repetition of the above-mentioned types of repetition. Methodical repetition is not the purpose of the study, because this repeated method of word formation is used to highlight certain phenomena, to strengthen the content of the statement. For example: “A handsome, neat, decent guide led him along the beautiful, neat roads of the city, on beautiful, neat, clean bridges, past the beautiful, neat houses to the house on the Canary where Mrs. Marietta lived” [5, p. 289].

In the book “Linguistic Encyclopedic Dictionary” reduplication is interpreted as follows: “Reduplication is a phonomorphological phenomenon having both incomplete (only one syllable of a word is repeated) and complete (the whole basis of the word is repeated) manifestations” [6, p. 408].

When reduplicating the word (the basis of the word) is used in repeated form, sometimes there is a vowel change (*daura-dauri* “back and forth” (in Indonesian), *chang-chung* (sound of beating utensils) (in Chinese)).

V.I.Nemchenko by reduplication means “a method of word formation, in which the repetition of a word or the basis of a word creates complex words” [7, p. 78]. The presence of its complete and incomplete forms indicates the possibility of reduplication together with affixing.

Scientists such as N.M. Shansky (“Basics of word-forming analysis” (Moscow, 1953), V.N. Troitsky (“Basic Principle of word-forming” (Moscow, 1963)) also consider reduplication (repetition) one of the ways of word formation. “Repetition of a word is not only a peculiar methodical technique aimed at strengthening the meaning of a word, but also one of the ways of new word formation” [8, p. 11].

A.S. Barkhudarov in the book “Word Formation in Hindi” writes that repetition of nouns and numerals can mean plural (for example, in Hindi *ghar ghar (men)* “in each house”, *bar-bar* “again and again”, *tukre-tukre (hokar)* (in many parts). In his view, the repetition of words served to enhance the substance of statements [9, p. 54].

In Chinese, repetition of nouns and numerals also has this feature, for example: repeating the word 家 *jia* “house” -家家 *jiajia* means “in every house”, repeating the word 步 *bu* “step”, i.e. 步步 *bubu* means “at every step”.

Therefore, reduplication (重叠 *chongdie*) is one way of word formation and comes from doubling the word morpheme [10, p. 84]. A lexical unit resulting from reduplication is called a reductive word or recurring word. A frequentative category is manifested through reduplication.

In Chinese, the phenomenon of reduplication is present in all word combinations and has a wide range of applications. In Chinese, the methods of word education based on reduplication are divided into two types:

1. Words formed from repetition of a single (simple) word: here there is a lexical unit with a new meaning. Such reduplication is considered one of the ways of word formation.

2. Words formed by doubling a word with two or more syllables (complex): in which the equivalent of a word emerges. Such reduplication is the way, which serves to create another form of word [10, p. 86].

However, the formation of reductive words in different parts of speech has its own peculiarities. Words of the first type are considered to have a new meaning, although they are repeated only phonetically [11, p. 119]. This has nothing to do with the previous two basic syllables. Consider the following examples:

往往 *wangwang* “often” (往 *wang* “to leave”),

花花 *huahua* “colorful”, “dazzling” (花 *hua* “flower”),

纷纷 *fenfen* “crowds”, “crowd” (纷 *fen* “lot”),

事事 *shishi* “all” (事 *shi* “case”),

洋洋 *yangyang* “wide” (洋 *yang* “ocean”),

落落 *luoluo* “independent” (落 *luo* “to pass”).

The second type of reduplication mainly includes kinship terms. They are formed from words with one morpheme (through the repetition of a morpheme) [10, p. 85]. 爸爸 *baba* “father”, 妈妈 *mama* “mother”, 姐姐 *jiejie* “sister (senior)”, 妹妹 *meimei* “younger sister”, 哥哥 *gege* “Older brother”, 弟弟 *didi* “younger brother”, 公公 *gonggong* “father-in-law”, 婆婆 *popo* “mother-in-law”, 伯伯 *bobo* “uncle” (father's brother), 叔叔 *shushu* “uncle” (father's younger brother), 爷爷 *yeye* “grandfather”, 奶奶 *nainai* “grandmother”.

From words formed by reduplication, it is necessary to be able to distinguish the following reduplicative lexical units: 偏偏 *pianpian* “as luck would have it, as luck would have it”, 常常 *changchang* “often”, 渐渐 *jianjian* “gradually”, 刚刚 *ganggang* “just now”.

According to Sun Changxu, the doubling of the morphemes in these words is only “a means of enhancing expressiveness” [11, p. 112].

In general, the phenomenon of reduplication further enriches the content of statements, gives originality to the speech tone of the speaker.

Let us now dwell on the role of reduplication in the typology of language. The concept of reduplication is clear today and does not have an unambiguous definition, to which all researchers subscribe [12, p. 54]. This concept refers to a dissimilar range of phenomena, including repetition within a word and between words. For example, in works on Russian and Slavic linguistics, the syllable with the concept of “reduplication” (Russian “giggle” as “laugh”, “whistle” as “whisper”), as well as affixal (Ukrainian “pokhoho”, “ponosnosnosti” “children”) or the repeated use of a certain word (Russian “walk-walk”, “go-go”, “far-far”, as “far-far”) and other types of repetitions (for example: Rus. “Stay buy and buy”, “Behind those trees there are forests and forests”, “Behind the trees there are forests, and behind the forests there are forests” [12, p. 59]).

Reduplication in terms of expression is not limited to repeating the same units or repeating only one basis and syllable [13, p. 26]. Repetitions are considered as repetitions related to the complete or partial repetition of the reductive sound, as well as “repetition of synonymous lexical units, that is, the creation of repeats of the value” [13, p. 37]. Their functional, structural, semantic capabilities are described only in general terms. The linguists saw no problems here for theoretical research. Most likely, for this reason, no special work of a general linguistic nature on repetition (doubling) was recorded. In the scientific literature, this issue is only two or three pages.

More broadly, the issues of reduplication (understood as an intraword repetition method) are discussed in the book “Languages of Southeast Asia” (Moscow, 1980). However, the phenomenon of reduplication of the Chinese language has not yet been fully studied, either theoretically or empirically. Repetitions within the word were not systematically studied in the Chinese language, and their description was limited to specifying the facts of individual species or repetitions.

At the same time, the universality of reduplication as a method of word formation in many, if not all, languages seems to be generally recognized. “Reduplication is common in different languages” [14, p. 208]. The same thought was expressed by E. Sepir: “There is no more natural evidence than the widespread prevalence of reduplication...” [13, p. 26]. There are also some universal signs of reduplication, for example, “...reduplication is often used as a means of changing the lexical value, expressing intensity, decrease, etc. [14, p. 208]”.

However, the study of language universals involves the identification not only of universal (isomorphic for different languages) but also of typical (allomorphic for different languages) properties of phenomena. While the first side of the question is covered in the scientific literature, the second side has not yet been explored. In particular, it remains unclear whether the intra-word repetition method is equally used in languages with different morphological constructions, or differently, to what properties of the language construction are related features of intra-word repetition. The arguments about the typological meaning of reduplication also remain contradictory to this day. For example, if N.V. Solntseva believes that “reduplication can be considered in a number of typological features of the language” [15, p. 79], then V.I. Belikov denies such a possibility [13, p. 34].

Further content of our research article will consist of reflections in the flow of questions described above, namely consideration of universal properties of reduplication (1), interpretation of its typical manifestations in various structured languages (2). In this case, in the study one of the ways of word formation, it is more logical to choose as the basis of typological comparison structural or morphological classification of languages.

1. Rather common structural types of reduplication in one form or another are represented in different languages. In all (or most) languages there are such types of reduplication as full (full reduplicate repetition: syllable, morphemes, bases or words), incomplete (partial reduplicator repetition) and divergent (the appearance of a reduplicate by changing the sound composition). For example, complete reduplication: small “labu-labu” “clay pot”, drilled “dima-dima” “in vain”: Rus. “white-white”) “white”; incomplete reduplication: Chinese. 糊里糊涂 *hu li hutu* “stupid”, “useless”; divergent reduplication: Indonesian. “colak-culing” “messy”, Russian. “back - forth” and “back and forth”. In a language, parts of a word can be edited via affixes (complicated

reduplication). For example, in the Khas language, “tam-shi-tam” means “more and more”, “more and more”, in the Buryat “ula-anhaa ulan” – “very red”, in the Russian “black-pre-black” – “very black”.

Semantic functions of reduplication are varied. These range from the expression of grammatical meanings to the modification or variation of lexical semantics [16, p. 56]. However, there are strong similarities in the basic meanings of repeated words in many languages. In semantic universals, the use of repetition to reinforce a trait undoubtedly points to a connection between this method and the “idea of measure and quantity” [13, p. 22]. The following universals of semantics of models of reduplication were proposed by B.A. Uspensky: “In many languages, if (complete or incomplete) reduplication exists as a productive grammatical way of forming a word or form, the meaning expressed by this method also includes the meaning of quantitative or power changes” [13, p. 19]. This general idea (invariant value) is realized in different lexico-categorical classes in corresponding modified forms, i.e. “as the multiplicity, diversity and similarity for the meanings of the objects, as the degree of quality for the attribute meanings, as the remoteness and multiplicity for the processes, and in some cases as the change of the word meaning” [13, p. 25].

“The use of reduplication as a visual medium in the formation of imitative and figurative words led to its transformation into semantic universals. ... Reduplication is widely used in the education of ideophones and sound-absorbing words” [17, p. 87]. This is evidenced by examples from different languages: Kirgiz. “kobur-sobur” “mutter”, Russ. “ding-ding” - the word denoting the ringing of the bell, “tik-tak” - so “imitation of the sound of the clock”, “kud - kudah” - imitation of the sound of the chicken.

2. Among the universal structural and semantic manifestations of reduplication there are distinguished general invariant structural and semantic aspects of repetition with peculiarities peculiar to them. Observations have shown that in languages with the same morphological structure, the production patterns of reduplication are the same, while in languages with different structures there are distinct differences.

In isolative and agglutinative languages, reduplication occurs within the framework of the root morpheme [16, p. 23]. For example, in the isolative languages of Southeast Asia, the basic patterns of reduplication are in the form of a complete or divergent repetition of syllables of a single- or two-word. For example, a set of repetitions of adjectives in Chinese in the form of ABB. In Chinese, forms formed by combining a repetitive sound complex into a single-syllable (adjective, noun or verb) morpheme are much more common, for example: 凉丝丝 (地) *liangsisi (de)* “bitter”, 红扑扑 (地) *hongpupu (de)* “very red”, “flushed” and etc.

In isolative and agglutinative languages, researchers as special phenomena note the repetition of affixes. These languages are dominated by reduplication based on complete, incomplete, or divergent repetition of the stem root. The situation is reversed in inflectional languages, in which there is a high frequency of synonymic units, primarily synonymous affixes. As for mutually exclusive elements in inflectional languages with isolating and agglutinative languages (for example, the development of affixal elements in agglutinative languages and in languages with an inflectional construction, for example, the repeated words “sugarmahar”, “sifry-mifry” common in Russian), these are the phenomenon testifies to the tendencies inherent in a particular language, which can be understood through the diachronic prism of the dynamics of change in reduplicative models.

The representation of objectivity through the prism of the sign properties of objects and phenomena, apparently, led to the widespread use of a figurative word - onomatopoeia in isolative and agglutinative languages. For example, the Khmer “tak-tak” is an imitative word for the fall of drops; the Crimean “vao-vao” is an imitative word for the barking of a dog.

Structural, semantic and functional differences observed in different languages in terms of the method of intra-word repetition are due to their specific word-formation system and common typological features. Apparently, the differentiation of languages according to the nature of reduplicants (roots or affixes) is also connected with the development in these languages of one or another method of word formation. For example, while in languages of other typologies, the meanings conveyed by affixes are expressed in isolating languages through the reduplication of roots, in isolating languages, where affixation is limited and the addition of words plays a leading role, the main reduplicant is by right the word root used [14, p. 48]. While in inflectional languages with highly developed affixation and affixal synonymy, affixal repetition is more often used.

However, the structural specificity of reduplication is not determined by the productivity of affixation and inflection in the word-formation system of the respective languages. However, in classical agglutinative languages, in which the affixation method of word formation predominates, root-morphemic reduplication is more often used. For example, the Buryats. “hede-heden” “several”: Kirgiz. “kobur-sobur” (muttering sound), Chuvash. “shura-shura” “white”: Kazakh. “syra-syra” - “in a row”. The fact that reduplication is structurally not directly related to the typology of word-formation methods indicates that its structural (including

semantic) originality is largely determined by the general typological properties of languages, and word-formation methods in them appear in relatively separate manifestations.

Such general typological traits, as V.M.Solntseva points out, consist of three types of interdependent relationships. These are: hierarchical (construction of units), syntagmatic (relationships of units of the same level in a sentence) and paradigmatic (ways of grouping units into different classes) [12, p. 29]. These relations create the conditions for the development of the merged and agglutinative methods of combining morphemes in different languages [12, p. 39]. In our view, these relationships are important in order for a model of reduplication to prevail. In other words, such important typological features as syntactic autonomy, autonomy of root-base, methods of expression of syntactic relations and categorical characteristics of words, features of union of morpheme in structure of word forms, have a great influence on the development of certain models of intra-verbal repetition.

The use of common root bases (root words) in isolative and agglutinative languages speeds up the development of root reduction in these languages.

CONCLUSIONS

The stated reasoning about the role of reduplication in the typology of language leads to the following conclusions:

1. The universality of the method of reduplication and its structural, semantic-functional uniqueness in the languages of various typologies allow to consider reduplication as one of the typological features in the classification of languages.

2. The languages of different typologies differ not only in the specific application of the general (or majority) method of intra-word repetition, but also in the degree to which this method is related to other typological indicators.

3. The intra-word repetition method is undoubtedly more widely used in languages where word formation is the main method of word formation. In languages where there is no method of verbalization, reduplication is usually quite limited. For example, in the Inuit-Aleutian group of Paleo-Asian languages, there is no way of adding words, and the method of repetition occurs only in exclamatory words: Eskimo. “kuk-kuk” is a signal for the appearance of a sea animal on the surface of the water, Aleut. “ka-ka!” - a sound indicating the need to turn right. However, at the same time, the productivity of the way words are added in a language does not mean that reduplication in that language has a wide scope of application. For example, the Ket language (one of the Paleozoic languages) has a method of adding words, but hardly any method of reduplication (except exclamation words).

4. The analysis of the phenomenon of reduplication, taking into account the reductive models inherent in flective languages, can only correct its common definition as a “phonomorphological phenomenon”.

5. On the basis of structural-semantic and functional manifestations of reduplication, the following new definition can be proposed: reduplication is a way of forming a word or form consisting of repetition of morphemes, words or their elements (sounds, syllables), affixes or whole words. The productivity of a particular type of reduplication depends on the specific morphological structure of the language.

6. Structural reduplication can be classified as follows:

1. Reduplication associated with full or partial repetition of reductive sound:

Simple (not complicated) reduplication:

a) complete reduplication - reduplication of the root-morpheme or root-word, reduplication of the sound complex;

b) incomplete reduplication - reduplication of one sound, one syllable or a longer part of reduplication (without the formation of divergent parts);

c) divergent reduction - repetition in combination with a change in the composition of the reducing sound (including changes in tone), i.e., reduplication, which implies the formation of divergent parts).

Complex reduplication - repetition with the participation of auxiliary morphemes (affixes, semi-affixes).

2. Reduplication that is not associated with repetition of reduplicate is the repetition of synonymous lexical units.

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